

European Digital Rights – Human Rights for a Digital Age?

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Abstract

Technological innovations in assistive technologies create great opportunities, but they come with big challenges too. One of them is the proper protection of the rights of all stakeholders, but especially those belonging to vulnerable groups, i.e., senior citizens and people with disabilities. It may be beneficial to draft a new catalogue of fundamental rights. This paper examines if the European Declaration on Digital Rights may be the first step in that direction. For that purpose, Human Rights (HR) are discussed as supreme principles of legal systems, from the perspectives of philosophy and law. Secondly, two key features of the European HR law system are identified. Thirdly, legal aspects of the Declaration are examined, and compared with HR law. The legal analysis of the Declaration is divided into four steps: the legal position of the Declaration, material analysis of the proposed Digital Rights, enforcement mechanisms, and comparison with the European Convention on Human rights. In conclusion, the importance of the Declaration and the potential of European Digital Rights are acknowledged, and the most needed amendments are proposed.

Keywords

Human Rights, Digital Rights, EU law, data protection, AI.

Introduction

Technological innovations in assistive technologies (AT) create great opportunities, but they come with big challenges too. While they allow people to be more autonomous and enjoy their lives, they may make people feel more dependent on technology. People often do not understand the technologies they use, which makes users feel insecure. At the same time, there are a variety of interests connected with AT. Balancing these interests and protecting the rights of all stakeholders is a challenge for the courts, legislature, and legal scholars.

The need for effective protection of rights and interests is especially important in the case of persons with disabilities and older citizens. First, people with disabilities face challenges and have specific needs. Because of that, there is a duty to provide them with enhanced protection (Limante, 30). Secondly, people with disabilities tend to feel vulnerable more often than others. While AT have the potential to elevate the users' quality of life, they also make them dependent on the system they use (Ake-Kob et al). Finally, AAL solutions deal with personal data. In many cases, it is data concerning health conditions, habits, and relations. Processing that data is considered by many as privacy intrusive and creates an imbalance between the user and the provider of the technology (Solve, Calo). Such deprivation of privacy could result in even increased feeling of vulnerability.

One solution to these challenges might be to draft a new catalogue of fundamental rights. That idea has been researched by many scholars (Mathiesen, Custers). The European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles (Declaration), proposed by the European Commission, is the first attempt to provide a full catalogue of probable new fundamental rights. There is no research on the Declaration and its potential significance. While it is still in its early stage, it is vital to initiate a discussion over it, and locate it properly in the context of ongoing discourse. This paper

aims to examine whether the rights listed in Declaration have the potential to become new Human Rights (HR), especially in the context of AT. For that purpose, HR will be discussed as supreme principles of legal systems, from the perspectives of philosophy and law. Secondly, some key features of the HR law system will be identified. Thirdly, legal aspects of the Declaration will be examined, and compared with HR law.

Discussion

Human Rights as the Supreme Legal Order

In many jurisdictions, including the American and European ones, Human Rights occupy a supreme position in the legal system. Out of many aspects of that supremacy, I propose to distinguish three: philosophical, jurisprudential, and institutional.

Human Rights law stems from the philosophical belief that some fundamental rights are common to all human beings (Hayden. Freeman). All people possess HR simply by virtue of their humanity (Tasioulas, 26. Donnelly, 10). For that reason, HR are inherited and inalienable. In consequence, “the possession of HR cannot be conditional on some conduct or achievement of the right-holder, a relationship to which they belong, or their membership of a particular community or group” (Tasioulas, 37). HR are inherited, so they do not need to be granted by any authority, but authorities must recognize and protect them (Jones). There is no agreement on what the most basic catalogue of HR is and to what extent they may vary in different societies (Wolterstroff 2008, 314. Tasioulas, 37. Sen.) However, there is a broad consensus that there are some basic, fundamental rights common to all people (Donnelly, 94. McCrudden, 667).

HR are considered fundamental rights on which the whole legal system is based in many jurisdictions. Some HR are listed in the constitutions, and they enjoy the status of constitutional rights. Multiple detailed regulations are sourced in the fundamental rights, i.e., procedural rules

of criminal proceedings stem from the right to access to the court and the right to defence (Johnson, 260). Respect for HR is considered one of the most vital requirements of democracy, but also the legitimacy of the law (Buchanan, 5).

The supremacy of HR also has its institutional aspect. National states are bound by international legal acts like the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), the American Declaration of the Rights and Duties of Man or the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR). Both at the UN level and regional levels there are bodies responsible for monitoring and protecting HR, to keep national states responsible for HR violations. American and European systems of HR protection give individuals the right to bring their complaints to specially designated, independent bodies. In Europe, it is the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR), whose judgements are binding for national states.

Key Features of HR Law in Europe

There are two characteristics of the European system of HR law that should be pointed out:

- 1) European HR law is principle-based, leaving national states some margin of appreciation.
- 2) Most HR do not have an absolute character, with exceptions like the right to life.

These features are essential to understand the European system of HR law, and to conduct an intended evaluation of the Declaration.

Rights listed in the ECHR have a character of legal principles, not norms. There are two main consequences of that. First, over time, the interpretation of the right may evolve, while the wording stays the same. As a consequence, the content of the right changes as well. In 2011, in *Bayatyan v. Armenia*, the ECtHR recognized the right to conscientious objection for the first time, considering social changes, and “developments both in the domestic legal systems of Council of Europe member States and internationally” (para 101). Second, states must recognize

all rights, but they have some margin of appreciation when it comes to the form of regulations. As McGoldrick notices, “in terms of whether the margin of appreciation applies and its width, it will be significant if the relevant law or policy is considered to reflect the ‘profound moral views of the people of the state’ (A.S. v Switzerland, para 241) or ‘concerns a question about the requirements of morals’ (Stübing v Germany, para 61)” (22). This margin of appreciation makes the law more flexible and allows it to respect social and cultural context, but also technological development (Shany. Hallström).

Most rights under the ECHR do not have an absolute character. There are only four rights that cannot be derogated: the right to life, freedom from torture or inhumane or degrading treatment or punishment, prohibition of slavery or servitude, and a prohibition of punishing without legal provision (Articles 2, 3, 4(1), 7). Legitimate limitations of rights and balancing them against each other are allowed under the ECHR. Balancing is a frequent practice at the ECtHR and requires judges to consider all interests involved (Cali). In the context of AT, it would mean that not only the interests of users and providers of AT shall be considered, but also caregivers, relatives, the general population, and the state. However, special consideration shall be given to the rights of vulnerable groups, i.e., people with disabilities (McGoldrick, 24. Alajos Kiss v Hungary, para 42).

Legal Analysis of the European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles

A legal analysis of various aspects of the Declaration is needed to assess whether it has the potential to have a position comparable to HR law. This research will be conducted in four steps. Firstly, it is vital to acknowledge the legal position of the Declaration, and by extension of digital rights (DR). Secondly, material analysis of DR will be undertaken. Thirdly, the possible enforcement of DR will be discussed. Finally, the Declaration will be compared with the ECHR.

The Legal Status of the Declaration

The European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles for the Digital Decade is a proposed joint document of three key institutions of the European Union: the European Parliament, the Council, and the Commission. Although the Commission has a right to legislative initiative, the Declaration does not constitute a legislative proposal *sensu stricto*. As the Declaration explains, it has a “declaratory nature and does not affect the content of legal rules or their application” (no 7 preamble), but rather is about “explaining political intentions” (no 5 Preamble). In its communication, the Commission explains that the Declaration should serve “citizens, businesses, public administrations and policy-makers” as a “guidance for a human-centred, secure, inclusive, and open digital environment” (1). The position of the Declaration should not be underestimated. There is a long-lasting tradition of interinstitutional agreements between the EU institutions, which may be of binding nature (Tournepiche. Driessen). Lenearts et al. notice that “where the Treaties do not expressly provide for an agreement to be reached, the legal force of an agreement will depend on whether the institutions intended it to be binding” (27.0500). Monar observes that if institutions do not want the agreement to be binding, they expressly state so (700-702). Therefore, although the Declaration is not binding for the EU States or individuals, it may bind institutions entering into the agreement.

Material Analysis of Digital Rights

The second step of the legal evaluation of DR is their material analysis. The main issue is whether DR are precise enough to be considered claimable rights. Secondary questions are if DR have the character of principles or norms, if they impose positive or negative obligations, and if the rights pertain to national states, the European Union, or other entities.

The declaration contains a preamble and six chapters, four of which are divided into subchapters. Each subchapter and undivided chapters consist of a statement followed by commitments. Commitments correspond with statements, and present EU policies that aim to achieve goals set out in the statements. The statements have various characters. Some of them are phrased in the language of rights: “everyone has the right...” or “nobody is to be asked to...”. Other statements employ “should”, and they express recommendations or the aims of the EU institutions. Out of twenty-three statements, seven are phrased in the language of rights, and sixteen in the language of recommendations. The seven rights listed in the Declaration are already guaranteed by other legal documents. The decision to phrase other statements as recommendations is in line with the intention of the Commission to prepare a declaratory document. The character of declaratory statements may be easily changed in the future by substituting “should” with “shall”.

The main question remains if the statements are precise enough to allow one to formulate a claim based on them. It is important to notice that fundamental rights are rarely as precise as statutory or procedural rights. Tharney et al. notice that the law is precise if it allows “ordinary people” to understand their obligations (353). Coleman suggests that such a test is appropriate rather for clarity than for the precision of the law (407-408). There is also no clarity on what “ordinary” or “average” could mean (Cohen). The history of HR law in Europe proves that the absolute precision of the law is a myth, and only case law may bring more clarity (Mellinkoff, 424). The language of the Declaration is not far from that of the ECHR or UDHR, and most DR are phrased with a precision comparable to HR law. For that reason, it is justified to call all statements “rights” or DR.

DR are principles rather than norms, as they are phrased in a relatively general way. Some of them are vaguer than others, i.e., “Everyone should be empowered to benefit from the advantages of artificial intelligence by making their own, informed choices in the digital environment while being protected against risks and harm to one’s health, safety and fundamental rights” (Chapter III). The rights connected with privacy and individual control of data and with the protection of children are the most precise ones (Chapter V). Some DR are negative rights (freedom of expression online, confidentiality of communication), and some are positive (right to access to digital technologies, right to education, training and lifelong learning). It is worth noticing that some negative rights of citizens come along with the positive obligation of service providers or states, i.e., Chapter IV guarantees everyone the right to freedom of expression online and obliges “very large online platforms” to “support free democratic debate online”, and to “mitigate the risks stemming from the functioning and use of their services”.

The Declaration states that “the promotion and implementation of the digital principles is a shared political commitment and responsibility of the Union and its Member States”. Commitments are addressed to the EU institutions that are cosignatories of the Declaration. Most DR concern issues remaining within the Member States’ competencies. It is also clear that the implementation of DR will impose new obligations on businesses, but also individuals. Because of the status of the Declaration, it may be binding only for EU institutions. For other entities, the Declaration may be a point of reference, and an inspiration for research or industrial standards.

Enforcement of Digital Rights

The existence of effective enforcement of rights is crucial for the ability of people to enjoy them. Without that, the rights will simply remain an idealistic manifesto. (Bilchitz, 4-6). The problem of enforcement is especially vital for people from vulnerable groups, including

senior citizens, and people with disabilities. Previous discussions show that currently the Declaration itself cannot be the source of legal claims. However, some DR are guaranteed through other legal acts, such as ECHR, the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU (Charter) or the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). These rights may be a source of claims enforceable in judicial proceedings, or a special procedure in the case of GDPR (Article 77, 82-84). Other DR may result in the liability of the EU institutions. Such liability would be primarily political, but because the Declaration may be legally binding, a judicial remedy cannot be ruled out.

Declaration and European Convention on Human Rights

To answer the question of whether DR may assume a role comparable to HR, it is beneficial to compare the Declaration with the ECHR. Three essential elements will be taken into consideration: legal character, precision, and enforcement mechanisms.

The Declaration and the ECHR have different legal characters and statuses. The ECHR is an international convention, legally binding for the states that ratified it. The Declaration is a declaratory document, a kind of policy statement of EU institutions, which may bind them as an interinstitutional agreement.

The precision of the language of both documents is similar. The scope and meaning of DR would have to be decided by the courts, as it has been with ECHR. The main difference in wording is that all rights from the ECHR are phrased as rights, while sixteen DR employ language more appropriate for recommendations or guidelines. It is a result of the character of the Declaration and can be smoothly amended in the future. DR are phrased precisely enough to consider them as fundamental rights.

There is an essential difference between the possible enforcement of rights from the ECHR and the Declaration. ECHR establishes the ECtHR and provides the basic rules of its proceedings. It also grants individuals a right to bring their complaints to national courts, and the ECtHR. The Declaration does not mention the issue of enforcement.

Despite the differences in legal character and provided enforcement mechanisms, there is an essential similarity between ECHR and the Declaration. They both aim to guarantee rights considered to be fundamental at the time, and in this way establish principles of the legal order.

Conclusions

Research presented in the previous parts of the paper allows the formulation of the following conclusions:

1. The Declaration is a policy statement of the EU institutions and should be read as such. It may be legally binding only for the signatories of the Declaration. However, even nonbinding documents are often used in EU policymaking as a point of reference. DR may be also used as a guideline by the Member States, industry, civic society organisations, and researchers.
2. Innovative technologies often require a regulatory response, and it may be necessary to introduce new fundamental rights in that context. Such a need and the content of these fundamental rights should be investigated in further research in the legal but also sociological and political domains. The alternative is to interpret existing HR more flexibly. However, this may not be clear to potential users of AT, who are especially vulnerable, and shall not only be protected but also feel safe.
3. If DR are to become the HR of the digital age, three crucial improvements should be made:

- a. First, DR must be formulated in a precise way allowing for the formulation of a claim.
- b. Second, the Declaration must be given a binding legal form, appropriate to the context and gravity of the matter. In my opinion, DR should be proclaimed at least in the form of a regulation. However, the optimal solution would be to include them in the EU primary law.
- c. Thirdly, the history of HR shows how crucial a well-working enforcement mechanism is. A mechanism analogous to the one of the ECHR should be introduced, guaranteeing individuals' right to bring their complaints to the Court of Justice of the European Union, or another specialised court that would be established.

In general, the Declaration is a step in the right direction. But further steps are required to make DR more precise, binding, and enforceable. DR established in that way may resonate and cause the so-called “Brussels effect” and also impact non-Europeans, as it was with GDPR (Gunst and De Ville. Bradford). That is a possible path for DR to become the HR of the digital decade.

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